

Encoding and Hiding Data within an Image and Conversion of Numbers

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Abstract: This paper describes about encoding and hide the encoded data within an image. Kali Linux hURL tool is used for encoding the data. hURL is a tool can be used for encode and decode. It is a kali Linux web application tool. The hURL is used for hexadecimal conversions and URL encoding and decoding. In security applications various encoding methods are used such as URL encoding, HTML encoding etc. For encoding Kali Linus provides a tool hURL. The steghide tool is used for hiding the encoded data within an image.

Keywords: hURL, steghide, conversions

I. INTRODUCTION

hURL is a tool that can be used for encode and decode. It is a kali Linux web application tool [5][6]. The hURL is used for hexadecimal conversions and URL encoding and decoding. In security applications various encoding methods are used such as URL encoding, HTML encoding etc. Kali Linus provides a tool hURL. The tool can implement common encoding and decoding operations such as URL, BASE 64, HTML. And it also supports conversions between binary, octal, decimal, and hexadecimal.

A. Features:

- Encoding
- Decoding

Conversions

- Binary to hexadecimal | Hexadecimal to binary
- Binary to int | Int to binary
- ASCII to hex | hex to ASCII

B. Some commands of hURL are:

- --color|--nocolor: This command enables or disable colored output [default is ENABLED]
- --help: This command displays help information
- man: This command extended help with

examples

- --version: Specifies version information
- -s: This command suppresses (display result only)
- -X|-x: ASCII to hex / hex to ASCII
- -B|-b: Base 64 for encode / decode
- -T|-t: int to binary / binary to int

The steghide is steganography tool for hiding the encoded data within the image [4]. The steghide is used for embedding the data. And the steghide is supported with jpeg, bmp, wav and au file formats.

C. Commands of the steghide are:

- Info, --info: This command specifies the information about a stego file.
- Version, --version: This command specifies short version information.
- Help, --help: This command display help screen.

D. Embedding

The embed command is used for embed the encoded data in an image.

Arguments of embed command:

- -ef, --embedfile filename: This argument specifies the file that will be embedded.
- -cf, --coverfile filename: This argument specifies the file name that will be used to embed data.
- -sf, --stegofile filename: This argument specifies the name of the created stegofile.

E. Extracting

The extract command is used for extract the received file that contain the embedded data.

I. LITERATURE REVIEW

Ameer Sameer Hamood[1] says about kali linux that is

Kali Linux is a Linux based operating system, mostly used in penetration testing. Developed by offensive security to replace the vulnerable back track Linux project. Kali Linux offers tons and tons of hacking and penetration tools and software by default. There are several type of kali Linux tools such as information gathering tools, exploitation tools, forensic tools, web application tools etc...

Arvind Kumar and Km.Pooja[2] do a work on steganography A data hiding technique. That specifies steganography is the art of concealing information and trying to do so hide the existence of embedded information. This is a cryptography alone is the best way to secure a message hides the content of the message, not the existence of the message. The original message is hidden inside a carrier changes in the carrier cannot be tracked. Analyzes the performance of some

steganography equipment. Steganography is a useful tool that allows for secrecy communicating information through communication channel. Integrating with secret image carrier image hidden image. Without the hidden image it is difficult to find recovery.

Kefa Rabah[3] says about steganography helps to hide encrypted content messages, images, keys, confidential data, etc.

II. OBJECTIVE OF PROJECT

The main objective of the project is to secure the data by encoding the data and hide the encoded data in an image this can achieved by using 2 kali linux tools that is hURL and steghide. The hURL is used for encoding and decoding the data. And steghide is used for embedded the encoded data into an image. It makes the data more secure because the data is encoded then it is embedded to an image. The image is sent to the receiver then the receiver extract the image for the data and then decode the data to obtain the original data.

III. WORKING CONCEPT

Step 1: Install hURL on kali linux by using the command

```
sudo apt-get install hURL.
```



```
josmy@kali: ~  
josmy@kali:~$ sudo apt-get install hurl  
We trust you have received the usual lecture from the local System  
Administrator. It usually boils down to these three things:  
  
#1) Respect the privacy of others.  
#2) Think before you type.  
#3) With great power comes great responsibility.  
  
[sudo] password for josmy:  
Reading package lists... Done  
Building dependency tree  
Reading state information... Done  
The following NEW packages will be installed:  
  hurl  
0 upgraded, 1 newly installed, 0 to remove and 1129 not upgraded.  
Need to get 19.2 kB of archives.  
After this operation, 191 kB of additional disk space will be used.  
Get:1 http://ftp.harukasan.org/kali kali-rolling/main amd64 hurl all 2.1-0kali1 [19.2 kB]  
Fetched 19.2 kB in 2s (7,820 B/s)  
Selecting previously unselected package hurl.  
(Reading database ... 296749 files and directories currently installed.)  
Preparing to unpack .../hurl_2.1-0kali1_all.deb ...  
Unpacking hurl (2.1-0kali1) ...  
Setting up hurl (2.1-0kali1) ...  
Processing triggers for kali-menu (2020.3.2) ...
```

Fig 1: Instalation of hURL on kali linux

sudo: (Super User DO)[7] command in Linux is generally used as a prefix of some command that only superuser are allowed to run. This is the equivalent of “run as administrator” option in Windows.

apt-get is a command-line tool which helps in handling packages in Linux. Its main task is to retrieve the information and packages from the authenticated sources for installation. Here APT stands for the Advanced Packaging Tool.

install : This command is used to install or upgrade packages. It is followed by one or more package names the user wishes to install.

Step 2: Encoding the data to be embedded with an image

There are many commands for encoding and decoding. The encoding makes the data more secure.


```
josmy@kali:~$ hURL -F 3.33

Original float  :: 3.33
Converted to hex :: 0xb81e5540
```

Fig 4: conversion between integer to binary and binary to integer using -T and -t commands of hURL. And conversion between float to hex using -F command of hURL.

- --color| --nocolor: Enable or disable the colored output default is enabled.
- -s: Suppress (Display result only)
- --version: Display version information

```
Converted to int :: 0
josmy@kali:~$ hURL -T 30

Original integer  :: 30
Converted to binary :: 00011110
josmy@kali:~$ hURL -t 1010

Original binary  :: 1010
Converted to integer :: 10
josmy@kali:~$ hURL -F 3.33

Original float  :: 3.33
Converted to hex :: 0xb81e5540
```

Fig 5: conversion between integer to binary and binary to integer using -T and -t commands of hURL. And conversion between float to hex using -F command of hURL.--color| --nocolor: Enable or disable the colored output default is enabled.

- -s: Suppress (Display result only)
- --version: Display version information

```
josmy@kali:~$ hURL -D --nocolor "josmy joseph"

Original  :: josmy joseph
2xURL ENcoded:: josmy%2520joseph

josmy@kali:~$ hURL -D -s "josmy joseph"
josmy%2520josephjosmy@kali:~$ hURL --help
::[ hURL - hexadecimal & URL (en/de)coder ]::
v2.1 @COPYLEFT -> fnord0 <at> riseup <dot> net

josmy@kali:~$ hURL --version
::[ hURL - hexadecimal & URL (en/de)coder ]::
v2.1 @COPYLEFT -> fnord0 <at> riseup <dot> net
```

Fig 6: Enable or disable the colored output using --color and --nocolor commands of hURL. And display the result only using -s command of hURL. And display version information using --version command of hURL.

V. CONCLUSION

The encoded data can be hiding in an image by using

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2 tools that is hURL and steghide. The hURL is used for encoding and decoding of the data and it can also use for number conversions. The stagehide is used for embedding the data into an image and it can also be used for extracting the information from the image. By using the hURL kali Linux tool, we can easily encode and decode URLs and we can easily perform the hexadecimal, decimal and binary conversions by using simple commands.

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